

1 **Shaping a gallium alloy and an ionic liquid into spherical**
2 **mirrors for future liquid-based telescopes – experimental**
3 **setup and demonstration in parabolic flights**

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11 **Abstract.** Space telescopes play a key role in the exploration of our universe, from imaging planets to gathering
12 spectra of distant stars. To date, all space telescopes are manufactured on earth and launched into orbit, with their size
13 constrained by the diameter of the launcher’s payload faring. This approach sets a hard limit on the telescope light
14 collection ability, which determines its resolution and contrast. The Fluidic Telescope (FLUTE) project proposes to
15 overcome launch constraints through in-space creation of large liquid mirrors, by utilizing interfacial physics under
16 microgravity conditions. In this paper, we present the design of experiments for the creation and measurement of
17 spherical liquid mirrors under microgravity, and their successful execution in parabolic flights. We describe the design
18 of the mechanical apparatus and experimental methods used to pin, constrain, and control liquid gallium alloy and
19 ionic liquid, as well as the optical technique used to reconstruct their surfaces *in-situ* using Shack-Hartmann wavefront
20 sensing. The results validate our experimental approach and show that the surfaces obtained under microgravity are
21 indeed spherical, as expected from theory, though parabolic flight conditions prohibit optical-grade liquid surface.
22 This set of experiments is a key milestone in maturing the FLUTE approach towards future extremely large liquid
23 space telescopes.

24

25 **Keywords:** Fluidic Shaping, optics, telescopes, space, microgravity, parabolic flight, liquid mirrors, Shack-Hartmann.

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28 **1. Introduction**

29 Space telescopes, in contrast to ground-based observatories, allow imaging and spectroscopy of
30 astronomical objects without the effects of atmospheric distortion, cloud obstruction, and the
31 attenuation of wavelengths outside the atmospheric window.^{1,2} Space telescopes typically utilize
32 mirrors rather than lenses, as they provide wide spectral ranges and zero chromaticity, while
33 minimizing weight.³ Among the most important parameters that determine the performance of a
34 space telescope is the size of its optical aperture.⁴⁻⁶ For example, with its primary mirror aperture
35 of 6.5 m, the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) provides an order of magnitude improvement
36 in light collection compared to the Hubble Space Telescope's 2.4 m primary mirror, and a threefold
37 increase in angular resolution. JWST's aperture size, which is larger than its launcher's payload
38 faring diameter, was possible due to its unique segmented mirror, which was designed to fold into
39 the launcher and deploy in-space.⁷⁻¹² While several future telescope missions rely on the same
40 folding principle¹³ and larger launchers are expected to come into service¹³⁻¹⁶, the 'holy grail' in
41 astronomy – the direct imaging of exoplanets – will remain out of reach even with these
42 advancements. It is estimated that to reach the required light collection ability to directly image an
43 exoplanet, a primary mirror of tens, if not hundreds of meters in size is needed.^{17,18} It is highly
44 unlikely that segmentation approaches could be extended to such scales, and moreover, the
45 production of such large mirrors may become an insurmountable task in terms of costs and labor.
46 Among disruptive ideas that were proposed to increase the size of space telescopes, a notable
47 concept is spinning liquid mirrors. By spinning a reflective liquid around a fixed axis in a

48 gravitational field, the free surface of the liquid takes the shape of a paraboloid.^{19,20} This concept
49 is advantageous since liquids provide naturally smooth surfaces, and can be fitted to any container.
50 Such ideas were demonstrated on Earth²¹, and also proposed for lunar-based observatories.^{22,23}
51 However, this concept requires consistent and precise rotation as well as gravity to maintain the
52 parabolic shape. Such telescopes can only be pointed in the zenith direction and are limited in size
53 by the Coriolis effect.²⁴

54 The Fluidic Telescope (FLUTE) project proposes an entirely different approach for constructing
55 liquid telescopes.²⁵⁻²⁷ The concept relies on the natural minimum-energy state of a liquid under
56 microgravity conditions, which drives its free surface to a static constant-mean-curvature shape.
57 By pinning the liquid to geometric boundary conditions and controlling the liquid volume, the free
58 surface can be shaped into a spherical concave mirror. We term this approach ‘Fluidic Shaping’.
59 FLUTE aims to construct space a telescope by forming a large spherical mirror from a reflective
60 liquid, without the need for rotation or otherwise ongoing actuation. Our initial mission concept,
61 FLUTE-50, aims to create a fluidic telescope with a 50-m diameter mirror, achievable with current
62 or near-term state of technology.

63 In previous work, we have developed the theory and demonstrated the creation of lenses by Fluidic
64 Shaping in a neutral buoyancy environment^{28,29} Recently, we have demonstrated the creation of
65 spherical liquid lenses in microgravity conditions on parabolic flights.³⁰ In this paper, we present
66 the next step in maturing this concept towards a practical space telescope - the development of a
67 system that creates and measures mirrors made of reflective liquids in microgravity. The system
68 is based on three main components: a suitable mirror liquid, a mechanical structure for liquid
69 pinning, and an optical measurement system.

70 Candidate liquids must have both high reflectivity and low vapor pressure to minimize their
71 evaporation in space. We have ruled out the use of mercury, due to its high toxicity and vapor
72 pressure that, albeit low, is still too high for space applications.^{20,22} Instead, we focused on liquid
73 gallium and its alloys, which are less dense, non-toxic, more reflective, and have significantly
74 lower vapor pressures. We also explore the use of ionic liquids, which are organic salts with good
75 wetting properties, low freezing temperatures, and extremely low vapor pressure^{31–33}, for creating
76 liquid mirrors in space. Ionic liquids, are already used as lubricants in the open space environment
77 onboard the International Space Station (ISS) and while not naturally reflective, they can be coated
78 to be used as mirrors.^{23,34–36}

79 Several important considerations of interfacial physics went into the design of our experimental
80 setup. The Fluidic Shaping approach requires precise pinning of the contact line of the optical
81 liquid to the bounding frame. While achieving such pinning was straightforward for the candidate
82 ionic liquids, special means were necessary in the case of the gallium alloy, due to its high surface
83 tension and low wettability^{37–40}. Furthermore, our setup had to be designed to protect the gallium
84 alloy from any exposure to oxygen, due to its high susceptibility to oxidation,^{37,41} as well as to
85 prevent its contact with any other metal on the aircraft due to its corrosivity.⁴²

86 In all cases, the concave surfaces maintained their shape only under microgravity conditions, and
87 thus needed to be analyzed *in-situ*. To that end, we designed an optical system based on a Shack-
88 Hartmann wavefront sensor, capable of measuring the liquid mirror surface topography under
89 microgravity in real time. We describe its construction and the methodology for deducing the shape
90 of the mirror from wavefront data.

91 We demonstrated the complete operation of the system under microgravity in parabolic flights.
92 Successful pinning of the liquids resulted in spherical surfaces that could be measured and

93 characterized by the optical system, even under the significant disturbances introduced in the
 94 imperfect microgravity environment of parabolic flights. With the mechanical and optical
 95 approaches validated, the system can now be further adapted for an in-space experiment for
 96 assessment of optical quality of fluidic mirrors under true microgravity.

97

98 **2. Theoretical Background**

99 The complete theoretical background for Fluidic Shaping can be found in Frumkin and Bercovici²⁸
 100 and Elgarisi et al²⁹. Here we present a brief derivation of the equations for the specific case of a
 101 single concave free surface in microgravity. Consider a reflective optical liquid filling a circular
 102 ring with radius R_0 and height H_0 , as depicted in Fig. 1. We define a cylindrical coordinate system
 103 with a radial coordinate r , azimuthal coordinate θ , and a longitudinal coordinate z aligned with
 104 the symmetry axis of the circular ring. Assuming that the optical liquid is pinned to the edges of
 105 the ring (the “pinning edge”) and that the system is rotationally symmetric, the total energy of the
 106 system can be written as the following integral,

$$E = 2\pi\gamma \int_0^{R_0} \left(\sqrt{1 + h_r^2} + \frac{\psi}{\gamma} h \right) r dr, \quad (1)$$

107 where $h(r)$ is the height of the liquid surface, and γ is the interfacial tension between the fluids.

108 The first term in the integral represents the surface energy of the free surface and the second term

109 represents a constraint on the finite volume of the optical liquid, with ψ is a Lagrange multiplier

110 associated with a constraint on the total liquid volume,

$$V_m = 2\pi \int_0^{R_0} h(r)r dr. \quad (2)$$

111 The Euler-Lagrange equation representing the energy minimum is given by

$$\frac{r h_{rr} + h_r + h_r^3}{r(1 + h_r^2)^{3/2}} = \frac{\psi}{\gamma}. \quad (3)$$

112 The left-hand side is the mean curvature of the surface, and the right-hand side is a constant,
 113 indicating that the surface is a spherical cap with a constant radius of curvature. The paraxial focal
 114 length of the resulting mirror is then^{43,44}

$$f = -\frac{R}{2}, \quad (4)$$

115 where R can be obtained from the implicit expression

$$V_m = V_o + \frac{\pi}{6} h_o (3R_o^2 + h_o^2) \text{sign}(R), \quad (5)$$

116 where $V_o = \pi R_o^2 H_o$ is the enclosed volume of the ring, and h_o is the maximal sag of the surface,

$$h_o \triangleq h(0) = |R| - \sqrt{R^2 - R_o^2}. \quad (6)$$

117 If $V_m < V_o$, then $R < 0$ and the resulting surface is concave, and if $V_m > V_o$ then $R > 0$ and the
 118 surface is convex. We are interested in the former, yielding a positive mirror with $f > 0$.

119
 120 **Fig. 1** Schematic cross-section of liquid pinned to a circular boundary in microgravity, forming a concave spherical
 121 mirror. Under microgravity, surface tension dominates and shapes the free surface of the liquid into a constant mean
 122 curvature surface. The radius of curvature is set by the volume of the liquid within the ring. In the case where the
 123 volume of the liquid is smaller than the volume of the ring, the result is a concave spherical surface.

124

125 **3. Experimental Hardware**

126 *3.1. Overview*

127 The experiment was performed on two parabolic flights onboard a reduced-gravity aircraft (Boeing
128 727-227 F, Zero-G Corporation, FL, USA). A flight consists of five to six sets of five parabolic
129 maneuvers, each providing between 10-20 seconds of free-fall. After every set, a short time of
130 several minutes in 1g is provided for resetting. Fig. 2 shows a photograph of the hardware setup
131 used to create and measure the liquid mirrors in microgravity. A ‘capsule’, the device containing
132 the mirror under test (MUT), was fixed on a mechanical stage within an imaging system based on
133 a Shack-Hartmann (SH) wavefront sensor. An inertial measurement unit (IMU) was connected
134 through a data acquisition system (DAQ) to a laptop, synchronizing and saving the acceleration
135 and SH data in real time. All the hardware was fixed to an optical breadboard, which was enclosed
136 by acrylic plates attached to an aluminum frame. The breadboard was connected to an aluminum
137 bottom plate through four wire rope dampers, used to isolate the system and reduce external
138 vibrations and disturbances as much as possible. The bottom plate was bolted to the aircraft floor.
139 We used a gallium alloy and an ionic liquid as working liquids that are relevant for space
140 applications, as well as water as a reference. We tested 6 different capsules, each with a different
141 mirror configuration (different diameter, liquid, and pinning approach). Since it is extremely
142 challenging to perform complex manual operations during the aircraft’s maneuvers, each capsule
143 was tested in all parabolas within a given set and was replaced with a different capsule during the
144 reset time between sets.

145

146 **Fig. 2** The setup hardware used to create and measure liquid mirrors in microgravity. The imaging system was installed
147 on an optical breadboard within an aluminum enclosure. Inside the imaging system, a sealed capsule was used to
148 create and contain the liquid mirrors under test. A laptop connected to an inertial measurement unit (IMU) and a data
149 acquisition unit (DAQ) were used to capture and save data in real time. The entire apparatus was fixed to an aluminum
150 bottom plate through wire rope isolation dampers, used to reduce external disturbances as much as possible. The
151 bottom plate was bolted directly to the aircraft floor.

152

153 *3.2. Material selection and considerations*

154 Pure gallium has a melting temperature of about 30°C, which would have required heating to keep
155 it in liquid form. For this reason, we used Galinstan, an alloy composed of 68.5% Ga, 21.5% In
156 and 10.0 Sn% by weight (Suzhou Haichuan Rare Metal Products Co., Ltd., China). Galinstan has
157 a melting temperature of -19°C and remains liquid in room temperature. Gallium and its alloys

158 present several challenges for use in liquid mirrors: (1) gallium readily oxidizes at low ppm levels
159 of oxygen; (2) it exhibits poor wetting of other surfaces making it difficult to pin to a prescribed
160 boundary, and it is corrosive to most metals.^{37,40–42} Thus, the experimental setup must account for
161 these challenges and maintain the Galinstan in an inert environment, ensure its pinning to the
162 mirror frame, and prevent it from coming in contact with the aircraft’s aluminum components. For
163 brevity, we will hereafter refer to the specific gallium alloy simply as ‘gallium’, but emphasize
164 that only Galinstan with the abovementioned composition was used throughout.

165 Ionic liquids are a broad family of chemical compounds composed of purely ionic species and vary
166 significantly in their chemical composition and physical properties. The ionic liquid we used in
167 our experiments is 1-Ethyl-3-methylimidazolium ethyl sulfate (EMIES, Sigma-Aldrich, USA),
168 due to its low-toxicity and common use in laboratory research.⁴⁵ In contrast to gallium and its
169 alloys, EMIES is easy to handle, not corrosive, does not oxidize, and readily wets many types of
170 materials. However, its low reflectance introduces additional requirements on the sensitivity of the
171 optical system.

172

173 *3.3. Capsules design*

174 Fig. 3 presents the structures of the different capsule designs used to form the mirrors from gallium,
175 ionic liquid, and water. As depicted in Fig. 3(a)-(b), the external stainless steel case of the gallium
176 capsule included an optical window embedded in its top part, and three valves – A, B and C –
177 were used to control the flow of fluids into and out of the capsule. Valves A and B were used to
178 control the vacuum and nitrogen gas lines respectively, whereas valve C was used to control the
179 flow of liquid gallium in and out of the system. The gallium was stored in a large stainless-steel
180 container (not shown in the figure) with a port at the bottom. Since gallium oxide and most other

181 potential contaminants have a lower density than gallium, they tend to float to the surface, keeping
182 the bottom portion clean. Filling the capsule was done on the ground, under gravity. We first
183 purged it from oxygen by repeatedly evacuating it to a vacuum level of 10^{-3} torr and flushing it
184 with ultra-high purity nitrogen (UHP, 99.9999% purity). After three such cycles, we performed
185 one last evacuation, and, under vacuum, connected the container port to valve C and allowed clean
186 gallium to flow from the container to the capsule. Within the capsule, an internal conduit delivered
187 the gallium to the floor of an internal chamber containing a ‘pinning ring’. After the chamber was
188 filled with the desired volume of gallium, we closed valve C and filled the remaining chamber
189 volume with nitrogen through valve B, reaching a positive gauge pressure of 0.1 atm. The pinning
190 ring was designed to force the gallium to remain pinned by one of two approaches – geometric
191 pinning, or surface adhesion. Fig. 3(c) shows a schematic cross-section of the capsule equipped
192 with the ‘geometric pinning ring’ - a stainless-steel cylindrical part with a counterbore hole. The
193 bottom portion of the ring is wider than the upper part and includes an undercut region, forming a
194 circumferential channel around a sharp tapered ‘pinning edge’. During the filling process on the
195 ground, we filled gallium until the liquid level (depicted by the black dashed line in the Fig.) was
196 above the top surface of the circumferential channel. Since this step was performed under vacuum,
197 gallium fully filled the circumferential channel without any trapped gases. Nitrogen was then
198 allowed to fill the volume above the free surface of the gallium. Under microgravity, we aspirated
199 gallium by opening valve C, and let the internal nitrogen pressure push gallium into an empty vial
200 (not shown in the Fig.). The angle of the gallium at its contact point is determined purely
201 geometrically by its volume that is prescribed by the desired mirror curvature (see the Theoretical
202 Background section). The taper angle of the sharp edge ensures that even for very concave
203 surfaces, the liquid will far exceed its receding contact angle and will thus remain pinned.⁴⁶ The

204 imaging system was measuring the mirror in real time, allowing us to set the aspirated volume
205 such that the mirror's curvature would fall within the focal range of the optical system. After
206 reaching the desired curvature, we stopped all external actuations and took optical measurements
207 of the liquid surface for the remainder of the maneuver.

208 Despite its poor wetting properties, we also attempted the use of a more traditional approach for
209 pinning gallium, using a simple bounding ring. We found empirically that gallium can wet copper
210 to some extent, and while gallium is corrosive to copper, the corrosion process is sufficiently slow
211 relative to our experimental time.⁴² Fig. 3(d) depicts a schematic cross-section of the capsule
212 equipped with an adhesion ring made of copper. During the gallium filling process on the ground,
213 we filled gallium until the liquid level reached the top edge of the ring. We then aspirated a small
214 volume of gallium, which remained pinned to the upper edge of the cylinder due to chemical
215 adhesion with the copper surface. Under gravity, the shape of the surface is nearly flat, except for
216 within a capillary length from the edge, where a meniscus is formed due to pinning (as depicted
217 by the black dashed line). In microgravity, the liquid surface was naturally driven by surface
218 tension to form a concave spherical mirror, without the need for further actuation. Fig. 3(e) shows
219 a photograph of the gallium capsule after filling it on the ground, under gravity. The inert vacuum
220 environment within the capsule prevented the gallium from oxidizing, resulting in a clean specular
221 mirror surface. A video showing the filling process is available in the Supplementary Information.
222 We also used the same adhesion ring design for the ionic liquid and water experiments, although
223 without the vacuum and nitrogen cycles (and using a plastic ring instead of copper). Unlike
224 gallium, these liquids do not oxidize and easily wet plastic surfaces. However, these liquids are
225 also optically transparent, and as such exhibit much lower reflectance than gallium – only ~2% in
226 the visible range. To be able to measure such surfaces, stray light and parasitic reflections from

227 the capsule window must be orders of magnitude weaker than the main beam reflected off the
 228 liquid surfaces. To eliminate ghosts, we matched the light source wavelength (590 nm) and the
 229 anti-reflective coating of the capsule window (Edmund VIS0), yielding reflectance of the capsule
 230 window of less than 0.02% for all practical angles of incidence. In addition, the entire optical train
 231 was isolated from ambient stray light by black hoods.

232
 233 **Fig. 3** The liquid capsules used to form the mirrors under test. (a) Isometric and (b) cross-section CAD views of the
 234 gallium capsule. The gas-tight thick stainless-steel casing prevents the gallium from oxidizing or from corroding other
 235 surfaces. Valves A and B are used to control vacuum and nitrogen flow, and valve C is used to control the flow of
 236 gallium. An optical window is embedded in the top part of the capsule for optical access. (c) A schematic cross-section
 237 of the ‘geometric pinning ring’ within the capsule. On the ground, we filled gallium under vacuum, until the liquid
 238 level was above the top surface of the circumferential channel. We then filled the remaining volume with nitrogen.
 239 Under microgravity, we aspirated gallium out of the capsule, which caused the liquid level to descend. The geometry
 240 of the ring constrained the gallium to remain pinned to the edge, forming a spherical concave mirror. (d) A schematic
 241 cross-section of the ‘adhesion ring’ within the capsule. On the ground, we used the same procedure as before to create
 242 an inert nitrogen environment. We filled gallium up to the top surface of the ring and then aspirated a small volume
 243 of gallium, forming a nearly flat liquid surface with a small meniscus near the edges. Under microgravity, the flat

244 surface was naturally driven to a concave spherical shape. (e) A photograph of the filled gallium capsule on the ground
245 before the experiment.

246

247

248 3.4. Optical design

249 Fig. 4 presents the imaging system used for the reconstruction of the liquid mirror topography.

250 Fig. 4(a) shows a ray-tracing diagram of the optical train. A fiber-coupled monochromatic LED

251 (source: M590F3, $\lambda=590$ nm; fiber: M129L01 $\text{\O}200$ μm multimode fiber patch, Thorlabs, USA)

252 was used as a point source, and was positioned at the focal point of a 90° off-axis parabolic mirror

253 (MPD249-G01, $f=4''$, Thorlabs, USA) to form a 50-mm diameter collimated beam with a planar

254 wavefront (confirmed to have a wavefront error below $\lambda/10$). The beam passed through an

255 adjustable iris and a 3'' pellicle beam splitter (Nitrocellulose, #39-489, Edmund Optics, USA),

256 tilted by 45° to the optical axis. The transmitted beam was dumped into a black diffuse cover (not

257 shown in the figure), with the reflected beam incident on the mirror under test (MUT) and reflected

258 off it to form a converging wavefront. The beam then passed again through the beam splitter, a

259 relay lens (TRS254-040-A-ML Steinheil Achromatic Triplet, Thorlabs, USA), and finally into the

260 Shack-Hartmann (SH) wavefront sensor (WFS40-7AR, Thorlabs, USA). We set the distances l_m ,

261 l_s between the MUT, relay lens, and SH such that the mirror plane (the plane that passes through

262 the pinning edge within the capsule) was optically conjugated to, and therefore imaged onto, the

263 SH plane (the plane of the microlens array). This configuration allowed to properly transmit phase

264 information from the MUT to the SH without undesirable free-space propagation artifacts, as

265 depicted by the black dashed virtual rays.⁴⁷ There are infinite sets of l_m, l_s that would conjugate

266 the planes, and we chose values which yield a magnification ratio of ~ 4 , allowing us to measure
267 mirrors up to 45 mm in diameter with our 11.2 mm x 11.2 mm SH microlens array.

268 Since changing components or distances between them is not feasible during parabolic maneuvers,
269 the parameters of the system must be fixed. Using ray-tracing optimization in Zemax, under the
270 assumption of a paraxial MUT, we have selected a relay lens that provides the smallest aberration,
271 and for which the maximum angle at which rays enter the SH sensor will be within its allowed
272 range of 1° . This selection must account for the fact that the focal length of the MUT is highly
273 sensitive to inaccuracies in liquid volume, which is a function of the nominal focal length and
274 diameter. For example, in the case of a spherical mirror with a diameter of 50 mm and nominal
275 focal length of 200 mm, volume difference of less than 1 mL changes the focal length by more
276 than 60%. The selected relay lens (TRS254-040-A-ML Steinheil Achromatic Triplet, Thorlabs,
277 USA) provided a residual wavefront error under 60 nm ($\lambda / 10$) for MUTs with a measurable
278 diameter of up to 40 mm and focal length of 150–200 mm. For an extended focal length of 100–
279 1000 mm, the measured aperture must be reduced to 20 mm in order to obtain reasonable
280 aberrations of less than 295 nm ($\lambda / 2$). More information on the optical design can be found in
281 the Supplementary Information.

282 Since the only unknown surface in the optical train is the MUT, it is possible to reconstruct its
283 shape directly from the measured wavefront. A wavefront represents an iso-phase surface, and a
284 wavefront sensor thus provides a measure for the spatial variation of phase across its entrance pupil
285 plane.^{43,48}

286 Fig. 4(b) presents a schematic describing the approach for reconstructing the liquid surface
287 topography, by converting wavefront errors into topographic deviations. We first define a baseline
288 surface, relative to which the mirror surface will be measured, denoted by the dashed black line in

289 Figure 4b. We define a Cartesian coordinate system with the z axis aligned with the optical axis,
 290 such that the origin is at the minimum point of the baseline surface. We designate the topography
 291 of the MUT and of the baseline surface by $z(x, y)$ and $z^*(x, y)$, respectively. An arbitrary incident
 292 ray (parallel to the z direction) intersects the mirror plane (conjugated to the SH plane) at point A
 293 (x_A, y_A) . The incident ray is reflected off the mirror surface at point B , with an angle of incidence
 294 β (and thus the angle between the incident and reflected ray is 2β). We denote the intersection
 295 point of the ray with the mirror plane as C , at which the value of the phase is ϕ_C . At the same
 296 position (x_A, y_A) , we denote a point B^* on the baseline surface. If the mirror were to be replaced
 297 with the baseline surface, the angle of incidence would be β^* , and the phase at the intersection
 298 point with the mirror plane C^* would be ϕ_{C^*} . For convenience of illustration, Fig. 4 shows both
 299 triangles – ABC and AB^*C^* – to be on the same $x-z$ plane, and the baseline surface entirely
 300 below the MUT surface. However, the analysis hereafter is general and does not require these
 301 assumptions.

302 The phase difference between the points C and C^* can be related to the difference in the
 303 geometric distance traveled by the two rays from point A through $\Delta\phi = \frac{n \cdot (ABC - AB^*C^*)}{\lambda}$, where
 304 n is the refractive index of the medium (in our case, air) and λ is the wavelength.⁴³ The travel
 305 lengths for both rays, from A to C and from A to C^* , respectively, are

$$ABC = (z_A - z_B) \left(1 + \frac{1}{\cos 2\beta} \right) \quad (7)$$

306 and

$$AB^*C^* = (z_A - z_{B^*}) \left(1 + \frac{1}{\cos 2\beta^*} \right), \quad (8)$$

307 where z_A, z_B, z_{B^*} are the z values at points A, B and B^* , respectively. By subtracting Eq. (7)

308 from Eq. (8) and using the expression for the phase difference, we get

$$AB^*C^* - ABC = \frac{\lambda\phi_C}{n} - \frac{\lambda\phi_{C^*}}{n} = z_B \left(1 + \frac{1}{\cos 2\beta} \right) - z_{B^*} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\cos 2\beta^*} \right) - z_A \left(\frac{1}{\cos 2\beta} - \frac{1}{\cos 2\beta^*} \right). \quad (9)$$

309 Marking $z_A \triangleq H$ as the constant distance of the mirror plane from the $x-y$ plane, and denoting

310 $z_B \triangleq z$ to indicate it represents an arbitrary point on the mirror surface, Eq. (9) can be rearranged

311 as

$$z(x, y) = \frac{1}{P} \lambda \Delta\phi(x, y) + \frac{P^*}{P} z^*(x, y) + H(P - P^*), \quad (10)$$

312 where $\Delta\phi = \phi_C - \phi_{C^*}$, $P = 1 + \frac{1}{\cos 2\beta}$ and $P^* = 1 + \frac{1}{\cos 2\beta^*}$, and we dropped n since the ambient

313 medium is air (for which $n \sim 1$ ⁴⁹). $\Delta\phi$ in Eq. (10) is the difference between the measured phase,

314 and the phase that would have been measured if the surface was replaced with the baseline surface.

315 We note that in Eq. (10), $\Delta\phi$, z , and z^* are evaluated at the same $x-y$ coordinates, although in

316 reality they should be evaluated at slightly different locations (distances of AC and AC^* from

317 one another). Section III in the SI shows that this error is negligible compared to the discretization

318 error of the sensor. Since the incident beam is collimated, by choosing the baseline surface to be a

319 circular paraboloid,

$$z^*(x, y) = \frac{1}{4f} (x^2 + y^2), \quad (11)$$

320 the baseline wavefront, i.e. the wavefront associated with the baseline surface, will be purely

321 spherical^{43,44}. The difference between the measured wavefront and the baseline wavefront can be

322 directly related to the difference between the MUT topography and the topography of the baseline
323 paraboloid. We first use linear regression to find the spherical surface that best-fits the measured
324 phase according to the L^2 norm⁵⁰, also known as the ‘reference sphere’⁴³. We seek the value of
325 f in Eq. (11), such that the resulting baseline wavefront will be identical to the reference sphere.
326 In this process, we must account for the power of the intermediate relay lens, and thus used ray
327 tracing to compute the wavefront at the SH plane resulting from circular paraboloid mirrors with
328 different focal lengths f . This provided a lookup table that we used to determine the value of f
329 that would result in measured reference sphere at the SH plane. $\Delta\phi$ is therefore the measured
330 phase, after subtracting its reference sphere. To solve Eq. (10) and reconstruct $z(x, y)$ from $\Delta\phi$,
331 the distributions of angles of incidence $\beta(x, y)$ and $\beta^*(x, y)$ must also be known. For an arbitrary
332 surface, the angle of incidence can be calculated through inner product of the local normal \hat{n} with
333 the unit vector in the zenith direction e_z ,⁵¹

$$\beta(x, y) = \arccos(e_z \cdot \hat{n}) = \arccos \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial y}\right)^2 + 1}} \right). \quad (12)$$

334 Substituting Eq. (12) into Eq. (9) creates an implicit equation for z as a function of $\Delta\phi$ for each
335 coordinate (x, y) . To solve the equation, we use an iterative fixed-point numerical scheme. We
336 start with an initial guess of $\beta = \beta^*$, use Eq. (10) to yield an initial estimation for $z(x, y)$ and then
337 use Eq. (12) to yield a new value for $\beta(x, y)$. The result is then plugged again into Eq. (10) to yield
338 a new value for z . We iterate over this process until we converge to a solution for both $\beta(x, y)$ and

339 $z(x,y)$ The irregularity of the MUT can then be expressed as the deviation of $z(x,y)$ from its best-
 340 fit sphere (which we find through linear regression).

341
 342 **Fig. 4** The optical design of the imaging setup, and the approach for reconstructing the liquid mirror surface. (a)
 343 Schematic ray tracing showing the optical train. (b) A schematic showing a possible geometry (without the loss of
 344 generality) for reconstructing the mirror topography $z(x,y)$ from a baseline surface $z^*(x,y)$.

345

346 **4. Results and Discussion**

347 Fig. 5 shows surface reconstruction results of selected recorded frames of two mirrors, both 20
348 mm in diameter, that were formed during the flights – one mirror made of gallium and the other
349 of ionic liquid. Fig. 5(a) and Fig. 5(d) show the proper acceleration profiles (the modulus of the
350 acceleration vector as a function of time) from the moment their values descended below 0.1g, and
351 until after the selected frame was recorded. Although the gravity level remained below 0.05g for
352 at least 10 seconds before each selected frame, low- and high-frequency disturbances on the order
353 of ~0.03g were recorded. Such values are typical for the microgravity environment of a parabolic
354 flight.^{30,52} In the absence of disturbances, the expected surface shape predicted by the Fluidic
355 Shaping theory is a sphere. Fig. 5(b) and Fig. 5(e) show the reconstructed surfaces of the mirrors,
356 as well as their best-fit spheres. Fig. 5(c) and Fig. 5(f) show the ‘figure errors’, i.e. difference maps
357 between the surfaces and their best-fit spheres. The irregularity of each surface is then defined as
358 the root-mean-squared (RMS) of the figure error and serves as a scalar metric for the deviation of
359 each surface from a perfect sphere.

360

361 **Fig. 5** Surface reconstruction results for gallium and ionic liquid mirrors. (a)-(c) Results for one of the gallium mirrors.

362 (a) The proper acceleration as it was measured during the mirror formation. (b) The reconstructed surface of the

363 gallium mirror (blue) and the best-fit sphere to that surface. (c) The surface irregularity as the deviation of the surface

364 from its best-fit sphere. (d)-(f) The same for an ionic liquid mirror.

365

366 Table 1 summarizes the best results that were obtained for each mirror configuration (i.e., liquid,

367 pinning approach and aperture). The estimated measurement uncertainties are obtained via

368 numerical sensitivity analysis, as explained in section II of the SI. The results show that all liquid

369 surfaces are indeed spherical, with deviations on the order of microns. This agrees with the Fluidic
 370 Shaping theory under microgravity conditions and suggests that pinning conditions were indeed
 371 maintained. The focal lengths of the mirrors fall within the range measurable by the imaging setup,
 372 which further validates the system’s design and demonstrates the ability to define the curvature of
 373 the liquid surface under microgravity by controlling the volume of the liquid.

374 The deformations observed on the liquid surfaces are similar in magnitude to those estimated from
 375 our previous parabolic flights data ³⁰, and we assume that they result from liquid dynamics due to
 376 flight disturbances.

377

Table 1 Summary of mirrors shaped and measured under microgravity in different configurations.

Mirror configuration	Mirror aperture, mm	Measured aperture, mm	Focal length, mm	Surface irregularity, μm
Gallium – geometric pinning	20.0 ± 0.1	19.6 ± 0.6	806.8 ± 9.8	14.3 ± 0.02
	24.0 ± 0.1	20.0 ± 0.6	408.4 ± 8.1	6.85 ± 0.08
Gallium – surface adhesion	25.0 ± 0.1	20.0 ± 0.6	807.4 ± 9.1	9.07 ± 0.04
Water	50.0 ± 0.1	40.1 ± 0.6	316.7 ± 1.4	11.63 ± 0.05
Ionic liquid	20.0 ± 0.1	19.6 ± 0.6	337.5 ± 10.3	8.67 ± 0.04
	50.0 ± 0.1	20 ± 0.6	760.3 ± 9.7	15.00 ± 0.17

378

379 5. Conclusions and Future Outlook

380 In this paper we demonstrated the use of a dedicated experimental setup for creation via Fluidic
 381 Shaping and *in-situ* measurement of liquid mirrors in parabolic flights. We have successfully
 382 created mirrors made from different liquids and using different pinning approaches and proved

383 that in microgravity the resulting surfaces are indeed spherical, as predicted by our theoretical
384 model.

385 We observed liquid deformations on the order of microns on our mirror surfaces, which we
386 associate with flight disturbances. It is important to note that while the surfaces we obtained allow
387 to validate the operation of the setup, they do not represent the expected optical quality of liquid
388 mirrors in space; the proper acceleration disturbances as recorded by our IMU during the parabolic
389 flight are orders of magnitude larger than what could be expected in-orbit.^{53,54} In true microgravity
390 conditions, and with additional supporting optics, we expect that the liquid mirror would be able
391 to achieve a wavefront error at the instrument of below $\lambda / 10$ for general astrophysics, and below
392 $\lambda / 100$ for imaging.^{55,56}

393 An important conclusion from our experiments is that quantifying the way liquids respond to
394 external perturbations in a relevant environment is critical for any liquid-based space optics. As
395 recently shown by Gabay et al⁵⁷, the characteristic time scale τ in which a pinned liquid film
396 responds to dynamic actuations scales as $\tau \propto R_o^4 / H_o^3$, where R_o is the radius of the ring and H_o
397 is the thickness of the liquid. In our system, R_o was on the scale of 50 mm, and H_o on the order of
398 10 mm. For example, for a future 50-m telescope with the same film thickness (a plausible FLUTE
399 design point), the liquid would exhibit dynamics that are 10^{12} -fold slower. i.e. if the liquid can be
400 brought to an initial spherical form, then it can be considered a solid over any practical time scale.
401 As our experimental setup was proven to be effective in characterizing liquid mirrors *in-situ*, it
402 serves as a basis for future experiments to be performed on-orbit and aboard the ISS. In those
403 experiments, we intend to test properly scaled telescope designs in relevant environmental
404 conditions.

405

406 **Disclosures**

407 The authors declare no competing financial or non-financial interests.

408

409 **Code, Data, and Materials Availability**

410 The files containing the wavefront and IMU data, together with the software used to perform the
411 surface reconstruction are publicly available at <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12675183>.

412

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426

427

428 **References**

429 1. J. A. Tyson, "Comparison of Space Telescope and 4-Meter Ground-Based Telescope: Faint Galaxy Detection
430 and Photometry.," *PASP* **96**(581), 566, The Astronomical Society of the Pacific (1984) [doi:10.1086/131382].

- 431 2. V. Reddy et al., “Comparing Dawn, Hubble Space Telescope, and ground-based interpretations of (4) Vesta,”
432 Icarus **226**(1), 1103–1114 (2013) [doi:10.1016/j.icarus.2013.07.019].
- 433 3. L. D. Feinberg et al., “Space telescope design considerations,” OE **51**(1), 011006, SPIE (2012)
434 [doi:10.1117/1.OE.51.1.011006].
- 435 4. R. S. Polidan et al., “An evolvable space telescope for future astronomical missions,” in Space Telescopes and
436 Instrumentation 2014: Optical, Infrared, and Millimeter Wave **9143**, pp. 343–352, SPIE (2014)
437 [doi:10.1117/12.2057161].
- 438 5. Y. Song et al., “Review on on-orbit assembly of large space telescopes,” in AOPC 2019: Space Optics,
439 Telescopes, and Instrumentation **11341**, pp. 11–22, SPIE (2019) [doi:10.1117/12.2539065].
- 440 6. H. P. Stahl, “Optics needs for future space telescopes,” in Optical Manufacturing and Testing V **5180**, pp. 1–5,
441 SPIE (2003) [doi:10.1117/12.514277].
- 442 7. J. P. Gardner et al., “The James Webb Space Telescope,” Space Sci Rev **123**(4), 485–606 (2006)
443 [doi:10.1007/s11214-006-8315-7].
- 444 8. P. A. Lightsey, A. A. Barto, and J. Contreras, “Optical performance for the James Webb Space Telescope,”
445 presented at SPIE Astronomical Telescopes + Instrumentation, 12 October 2004, USA, 825
446 [doi:10.1117/12.550091].
- 447 9. P. A. Lightsey, “James Webb Space Telescope: large deployable cryogenic telescope in space,” Opt. Eng **51**(1),
448 011003 (2012) [doi:10.1117/1.OE.51.1.011003].
- 449 10. M. W. McElwain et al., “The James Webb Space Telescope Mission: Optical Telescope Element Design,
450 Development, and Performance,” PASP **135**(1047), 058001, The Astronomical Society of the Pacific (2023)
451 [doi:10.1088/1538-3873/acada0].
- 452 11. M. Menzel et al., “The Design, Verification, and Performance of the James Webb Space Telescope,” PASP
453 **135**(1047), 058002, The Astronomical Society of the Pacific (2023) [doi:10.1088/1538-3873/acbb9f].
- 454 12. C. J. Burrows et al., “The imaging performance of the Hubble Space Telescope,” ApJ **369**, L21 (1991)
455 [doi:10.1086/185950].
- 456 13. M. R. Bolcar, “The Large UV/Optical/Infrared (LUVOIR) surveyor: engineering design and technology
457 overview,” in UV/Optical/IR Space Telescopes and Instruments: Innovative Technologies and Concepts IX
458 **11115**, pp. 170–183, SPIE (2019) [doi:10.1117/12.2530456].
- 459 14. J. Yoo, “Characteristics of Starship System Development,” Journal of the Korean Society of Propulsion Engineers
460 **25**(5), 53–64, The Korean Society of Propulsion Engineers (2021) [doi:10.6108/KSPE.2021.25.5.053].
- 461 15. T. L. Team, “The LUVOIR Mission Concept Study Final Report” (2019).
- 462 16. *Pathways to Discovery in Astronomy and Astrophysics for the 2020s*, National Academies Press, Washington,
463 D.C. (2023) [doi:10.17226/26141].
- 464 17. C. Cavarroc et al., “Fundamental limitations on Earth-like planet detection with extremely large telescopes,” 1,
465 A&A **447**(1), 397–403, EDP Sciences (2006) [doi:10.1051/0004-6361:20053916].
- 466 18. B. Macintosh et al., “Extreme adaptive optics for the Thirty Meter Telescope,” in Advances in Adaptive Optics
467 II **6272**, pp. 201–215, SPIE (2006) [doi:10.1117/12.672032].
- 468 19. E. F. Borra, “Liquid mirror telescopes - Present and future,” PASP **99**, 1229 (1987) [doi:10.1086/132108].
- 469 20. E. F. Borra, “Liquid mirrors,” Can. J. Phys. **73**(3–4), 109–125, NRC Research Press (1995) [doi:10.1139/p95-
470 017].
- 471 21. P. Hickson et al., “The Large Zenith Telescope: A 6 m Liquid-Mirror Telescope,” PASP **119**(854), 444, The
472 University of Chicago Press (2007) [doi:10.1086/517621].
- 473 22. E. F. Borra and R. Content, “Lunar liquid-mirror telescopes,” in Space Astronomical Telescopes and Instruments
474 **1494**, pp. 219–227, SPIE (1991) [doi:10.1117/12.46727].

- 475 23. E. F. Borra et al., “Deposition of metal films on an ionic liquid as a basis for a lunar telescope,” *Nature* **447**(7147),
476 979–981 (2007) [doi:10.1038/nature05909].
- 477 24. D. Clery, “Telescope in India snares light in spinning mercury,” *Science* **376**(6599), 1260–1260 (2022)
478 [doi:10.1126/science.add4869].
- 479 25. “What is the Fluidic Telescope? - NASA,” <[https://www.nasa.gov/science-research/astrophysics/what-is-the-](https://www.nasa.gov/science-research/astrophysics/what-is-the-fluidic-telescope/)
480 [fluidic-telescope/](https://www.nasa.gov/science-research/astrophysics/what-is-the-fluidic-telescope/)> (accessed 8 April 2024).
- 481 26. “Fluidic Telescope (FLUTE): Enabling the Next Generation of Large Space Observatories - NASA,”
482 <[https://www.nasa.gov/general/fluidic-telescope-flute-enabling-the-next-generation-of-large-space-](https://www.nasa.gov/general/fluidic-telescope-flute-enabling-the-next-generation-of-large-space-observatories/)
483 [observatories/](https://www.nasa.gov/general/fluidic-telescope-flute-enabling-the-next-generation-of-large-space-observatories/)> (accessed 8 April 2024).
- 484 27. “NIAC 2023 Phase I and Phase II Selections - NASA,” <[https://www.nasa.gov/general/niac-2023-phase-i-and-](https://www.nasa.gov/general/niac-2023-phase-i-and-phase-ii-selections/)
485 [phase-ii-selections/](https://www.nasa.gov/general/niac-2023-phase-i-and-phase-ii-selections/)> (accessed 8 April 2024).
- 486 28. V. Frumkin and M. Bercovici, “Fluidic shaping of optical components,” *Flow* **1**, E2 (2021)
487 [doi:10.1017/flo.2021.1].
- 488 29. M. Elgarisi et al., “Fabrication of freeform optical components by fluidic shaping,” *Optica* **8**(11), 1501 (2021)
489 [doi:10.1364/OPTICA.438763].
- 490 30. O. Luria et al., “Fluidic shaping and in-situ measurement of liquid lenses in microgravity,” *npj Microgravity* **9**(1),
491 74 (2023) [doi:10.1038/s41526-023-00309-9].
- 492 31. J. Feder-Kubis et al., “Ionic Liquids with Natural Origin Component: A Path to New Plant Protection Products,”
493 *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **8**(2), 842–852 (2020) [doi:10.1021/acssuschemeng.9b04859].
- 494 32. P. Nancarrow and H. Mohammed, “Ionic Liquids in Space Technology – Current and Future Trends,”
495 *ChemBioEng Reviews* **4**(2), 106–119 (2017) [doi:10.1002/cben.201600021].
- 496 33. E. Nyberg et al., “Ionic Liquids as Performance Ingredients in Space Lubricants,” *4, Molecules* **26**(4), 1013,
497 *Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute* (2021) [doi:10.3390/molecules26041013].
- 498 34. J. Gingras et al., “Surface films of silver nanoparticles for new liquid mirrors,” *Colloids and Surfaces A:*
499 *Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* **279**(1–3), 79–86 (2006) [doi:10.1016/j.colsurfa.2005.12.043].
- 500 35. Y.-T. Yen et al., “Highly Reflective Liquid Mirrors: Exploring the Effects of Localized Surface Plasmon
501 Resonance and the Arrangement of Nanoparticles on Metal Liquid-like Films,” *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*
502 **6**(6), 4292–4300 (2014) [doi:10.1021/am406048s].
- 503 36. P.-P. Fang et al., “Conductive Gold Nanoparticle Mirrors at Liquid/Liquid Interfaces,” *ACS Nano* **7**(10), 9241–
504 9248, American Chemical Society (2013) [doi:10.1021/nn403879g].
- 505 37. E. F. Borra et al., “Gallium Liquid Mirrors: Basic Technology, Optical-Shop Tests, and Observations,” *PASP*
506 **109**, 319 (1997) [doi:10.1086/133893].
- 507 38. E. F. Borra, “The case for liquid mirrors in orbiting telescopes,” *ApJ* **392**, 375 (1992) [doi:10.1086/171436].
- 508 39. B. Yuan, Z.-Z. He, and J. Liu, “Effect of Electric Field on the Wetting Behavior of Eutectic Gallium–Indium
509 Alloys in Aqueous Environment,” *Journal of Elec Materi* **47**(5), 2782–2790 (2018) [doi:10.1007/s11664-018-
510 6134-8].
- 511 40. Q. Xu et al., “Effect of oxidation on the mechanical properties of liquid gallium and eutectic gallium-indium,”
512 *Physics of Fluids* **24**(6), 063101 (2012) [doi:10.1063/1.4724313].
- 513 41. S. I. Stepanov et al., “Gallium Oxide: Properties and Applications: a Review.”
- 514 42. Y.-G. Deng and J. Liu, “Corrosion development between liquid gallium and four typical metal substrates used in
515 chip cooling device,” *Appl. Phys. A* **95**(3), 907–915 (2009) [doi:10.1007/s00339-009-5098-1].
- 516 43. M. Born and E. Wolf, *Principles of optics*, Seventh anniversary edition, 60th anniversary of first edition, 20th
517 anniversary of seventh edition, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom (2019).
- 518 44. D. J. Schroeder, *Astronomical optics*, 2nd ed, Academic Press, San Diego (2000).

- 519 45. M. Wang et al., “Tough and stretchable ionogels by in situ phase separation,” *Nat. Mater.* **21**(3), 359–365, Nature
520 Publishing Group (2022) [doi:10.1038/s41563-022-01195-4].
- 521 46. L. G. Leal, “Advanced Transport Phenomena” (2007).
- 522 47. Joseph. W. Goodman, *Introduction to Fourier Optics*, 3rd ed., Roberts & Company (2005).
- 523 48. B. C. Platt and R. Shack, “History and Principles of Shack-Hartmann Wavefront Sensing,” *Journal of Refractive*
524 *Surgery* **17**(5), S573–S577, SLACK Incorporated (2001) [doi:10.3928/1081-597X-20010901-13].
- 525 49. “The refraction and dispersion of air and dispersion of air for the visible spectrum,” *Philosophical Transactions*
526 *of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, The Royal Society London (1939)
527 [doi:10.1098/rsta.1939.0004].
- 528 50. W. H. Press et al., *Numerical Recipes: The Art of Scientific Computing*, 3rd ed., in *Numerical Recipes - The Art*
529 *of Scientific Computing*, 3rd ed., Cambridge Press, New York (2007) [doi:10.1137/1031025].
- 530 51. Howard Anton, Irl Bivens, and Stephen Davis, *Calculus*, 9th ed., Wiley.
- 531 52. C. E. Carr et al., “Acceleration profiles and processing methods for parabolic flight,” *npj Microgravity* **4**(1), 1–
532 5, Nature Publishing Group (2018) [doi:10.1038/s41526-018-0050-3].
- 533 53. R. DeLombard et al., “Microgravity Environment on the International Space Station,” presented at 42nd AIAA
534 *Aerospace Sciences Meeting and Exhibit*, AIAA [doi:10.2514/6.2004-125].
- 535 54. Kevin McPherson, Eric Kelly, and Jennifer Keller, “Acceleration Environment of the International Space
536 *Station*,” presented at 47th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting Including The New Horizons Forum and
537 *Aerospace Exposition*, 5 January 2009, Orlando, Florida , USA, AIAA [doi:https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2009-957].
- 538 55. S. B. Shaklan et al., “The Terrestrial Planet Finder Coronagraph dynamics error budget,” in *Techniques and*
539 *Instrumentation for Detection of Exoplanets II* **5905**, pp. 110–121, SPIE (2005) [doi:10.1117/12.617890].
- 540 56. I. Lajinja et al., “Wavefront tolerances of space-based segmented telescopes at very high contrast: Experimental
541 *validation*,” *A&A* **658**, A84, EDP Sciences (2022) [doi:10.1051/0004-6361/202142150].
- 542 57. I. Gabay et al., “Dynamics of fixed-volume pinned films – dealing with a non-self-adjoint thin-film problem,” *J.*
543 *Fluid Mech.* **969**, A17 (2023) [doi:10.1017/jfm.2023.550].
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- 546

547 **Caption List**

548

549 **Fig. 1** Schematic cross-section of liquid pinned to a circular boundary in microgravity, forming a concave spherical
550 mirror. Under microgravity, surface tension dominates and shapes the free surface of the liquid into a constant mean
551 curvature surface. The radius of curvature is set by the volume of the liquid within the ring. In the case where the
552 volume of the liquid is smaller than the volume of the ring, the result is a concave spherical surface.

553

554 **Fig. 2** The setup hardware used to create and measure liquid mirrors in microgravity. The imaging system was installed
555 on an optical breadboard within an aluminum enclosure. Inside the imaging system, a sealed capsule was used to
556 create and contain the liquid mirrors under test. A laptop connected to an inertial measurement unit (IMU) and a data
557 acquisition unit (DAQ) were used to capture and save data in real time. The entire apparatus was fixed to an aluminum
558 bottom plate through wire rope isolation dampers, used to reduce external disturbances as much as possible. The
559 bottom plate was bolted directly to the aircraft floor.

560

561 **Fig. 3** The liquid capsules used to form the mirrors under test. (a) Isometric and (b) cross-section CAD views of the
562 gallium capsule. The gas-tight thick stainless-steel casing prevents the gallium from oxidizing or from corroding other
563 surfaces. Valves A and B are used to control vacuum and nitrogen flow, and valve C is used to control the flow of
564 gallium. An optical window is embedded in the top part of the capsule for optical access. (c) A schematic cross-section
565 of the ‘geometric pinning ring’ within the capsule. On the ground, we filled gallium under vacuum, until the liquid
566 level was above the top surface of the circumferential channel. We then filled the remaining volume with nitrogen.
567 Under microgravity, we aspirated gallium out of the capsule, which caused the liquid level to descend. The geometry
568 of the ring constrained the gallium to remain pinned to the edge, forming a spherical concave mirror. (d) A schematic
569 cross-section of the ‘adhesion ring’ within the capsule. On the ground, we used the same procedure as before to create
570 an inert nitrogen environment. We filled gallium up to the top surface of the ring and then aspirated a small volume
571 of gallium, forming a nearly flat liquid surface with a small meniscus near the edges. Under microgravity, the flat
572 surface was naturally driven to a concave spherical shape. (e) A photograph of the filled gallium capsule on the ground
573 before the experiment.

574

575

576 **Fig. 4** The optical design of the imaging setup, and the approach for reconstructing the liquid mirror surface. (a)

577 Schematic ray tracing showing the optical train. (b) A schematic showing a possible geometry (without the loss of

578 generality) for reconstructing the mirror topography $z(x, y)$ from a baseline surface $z^*(x, y)$.

579

580 **Fig. 5** Surface reconstruction results for gallium and ionic liquid mirrors. (a)-(c) Results for one of the gallium mirrors.

581 (a) The proper acceleration as it was measured during the mirror formation. (b) The reconstructed surface of the

582 gallium mirror (blue) and the best-fit sphere to that surface. (c) The surface irregularity as the deviation of the surface

583 from its best-fit sphere. (d)-(f) The same for an ionic liquid mirror.

584

585 **Table 1** Summary of mirrors shaped and measured under microgravity in different configurations.